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Short communication

SHARED LITERARY READING IN THE AGE OF DIGITIZATION

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INTRODUCTION

Literature is a form of human expression often regarded as one of the most complex and most rewarding verbal practices. In adulthood, reading literature may be considered a solitary act of engagement with art even though we first encounter literature through shared reading practices, either with parents, caregivers, or teachers (Billington, Davis, & Farrington, 2013).

Shared Reading programs can be referred to as a distinct type of reading activity that usually includes a facilitator and 6 to 12 participants who then one at the time read literature aloud and share their personal experiences. It differs substantially from the traditional reading club model where group members gather to discuss a piece of literature that they had previously read in the privacy and comfort of their own homes. In the Shared Reading programs, participants actively read literature on the spot at their convenience and create a welcoming atmosphere where each group member feels safe to take part in reading and express their thoughts and emotions about the literary text through an open-ended discussion (Skjerdingsstad & Tangerås, 2019).

Reading literature is a unique form of interaction with art as it instigates psychological change (Billington, 2019). This change emerges from exposure to stylistic and narrative variations in literary texts (Miall & Kuiken,

1994). The recent proliferation of interdisciplinary studies, jointly empowered by the expertise of psychologists, literary scholars, and neuroscientists, shed some new light on the connection between literature reading, prosocial behavior, and mental well-being. Mental well-being is a multi-dimensional construct that amalgamates cognitive and emotional capacities, which enable individuals to have a productive, fulfilled, and meaningful life. Furthermore, it involves the abilities of human beings to successfully navigate and build social relationships (Niqvist, Forsman, Giuntoli, & Cattan, 2013).

SHARED LITERARY READING AND SOCIAL SKILLS

A growing body of research indicates the important role of reading fiction in enhancing social skills such as empathy and social understanding (Billington, 2019). Reading fiction and novels have a potentially unique role in activating distinctively human ability to share affect with others and to understand other peoples' feelings, thoughts, and beliefs (Mangen, Kuzmicova, Nilsson, & Steenberg, 2018). The effects of literary reading on empathy seem to account mostly for narrativity (Koopman & Hakemulder, 2015). Narrativity is one of the aspects of literary texts that represents the ability to stimulate a narrative scenario in the mind of the reader. Narrativity is defined by the specificity, the degree to which a literary text focuses on a particular time, place, individual or an object, and by the dynamism, which refers to the relations between the subjects and objects in the text (Simon-Shoshan, 2012). These aspects of literary texts enable readers to chart a mental representation of characters and events and to transition themselves into these imaginary worlds. Therefore, literature, and perhaps especially novels and fiction, can be described as a powerful rhetorical device that has a function of a simulator for a plethora of social scripts (Koopman & Hakemulder, 2015). Some authors found that people who read literary texts written in a narrative mode were more likely to participate in social interactions and had better social support, one of the most fundamental contributors to mental well-being (Billington, 2019). These findings can, perhaps, be explained by better preparedness of individuals to take part in social interactions after having the opportunity to exercise their social skills in a distanced and safe literature environment. The primary feature of literary texts is that they, through storytelling and unfolding actions and events, allow readers to identify with

protagonists and calibrate their social skills by “putting themselves in someone else’s shoes” (Djikic, Oatley, & Moldoveanu, 2013). However, in order for a transformative reading experience to occur, a reader must be engaged with the literary text (Billington, 2019). Some research studies suggest that literary features such as unconventional metaphors, ungrammatical sentences, and distortions of the order of story events (foregrounding) can contribute to the engaging experience, and perhaps deeper involvement with reading. Furthermore, research evidence indicates that being absorbed and engaged with literary reading may prompt self-reflection and moral self-evaluation in readers (Balint, Hakemulder, Kujipers, Doicaru, & Tan, 2016). The ability to alter self-understanding and understanding of others seems to be a prerequisite for successfully recognizing and adequately responding to a range of social emotions. Social emotions have a prominent role in cooperation and group stability as they facilitate social relationships and motivate prosocial behavior (Krendl & Heatherton, 2017). Social emotions include a range of emotional states, such as guilt, embarrassment, pride, jealousy, and are best distinguished from basic emotions in their relative cognitive complexity. Successfully managing social emotions seems to be of vital importance in developing long-term relationships and eliciting adaptive social behaviors, foundational to positive mental well-being.

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

Review of the relevant literature reveals that most literary studies focused on the association between literary reading and intrapersonal aspects of mental well-being, such as self-reflection and empathy, while interpersonal aspects are somewhat neglected. Therefore, to address this research gap I propose to add a cognitive perspective to this research and further investigate the association between shared literary reading and the complex phenomenon of social emotions. Drawing on developmental perspective, examining effects of shared literary reading on socio-emotional skills has particularly important implications for educational policies and learning practice as research evidence from neuropsychological studies indicates that, unlike joy, fear, and disgust, many social emotions develop under the influence of socialization rather than genes (Krendl & Heatherton, 2017).

Complementing this, I propose to use the framework of embodied cognition to bring the perspective of digitization to this research. Embodied cognition is a new paradigm in cognitive psychology that addresses human cognition not as a secluded system of mental processes but the one that depends on the features and states of the human body and the environment (Wilson & Golonka, 2013). According to the embodied cognition theory, states of the body are foundational to the abstract cognitive states. In recent decades, as digital technologies rapidly develop, reading practices inevitably change alongside. Traditional paper books are replaced with digital devices (e.g., iPads, tablet computers, Kindle) that, due to a set of different properties or affordances, have potential to substantially change the reading experience and the way a reader interacts with the reading device (Kovac & Van der Weel, 2018). Indeed, some researchers found that reading literary texts on different reading substrates (e.g., iPad and paper) may influence readers' engagement and empathy (Mangen, 2018) The mechanisms of the effects of this radical shift in reading practices are yet to be understood.

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